

STUDIES IN TERPENES. PART VIII. BROMINE DEHYDROGENATION OF SOME TERPENOIDS

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That Baeyer-Villiger method of bromine dehydrogenation is based on false premises, there is no need to prepare 'fully' brominated derivatives, and it is incomplete bromination which offers a guarantee to successful aromatisation by heat and alkali have been substantiated by the aromatisation of 3-carene, α -pinene, terpinolene, and terpineol. Moreover, with bromine 3-carene furnishes *p*- and *m*-cymenes, and α -pinene, *p*- and *o*-cymenes. These two-way aromatisations are novel reactions in terpene chemistry.

Terpenoid bromides have been decomposed to *p*-cymene by heat (Wallach and Berthold, *Nachr. kgl. Ges. Göttingen*, 1915; Wallach, *Annalen*, 1918, 414, 206), by alkali (Wallach, *ibid.*, 1895, 287, 383), and by stepwise reduction ("the exhaustive bromination method") (Baeyer and Villiger, *Ber.*, 1898, 31, 1401). Examples are the formation of *p*-cymene from α -terpineol dibromide by heating (Wallach *et al.*, *loc. cit.*), α -phellandrene dibromide under the influence of alkali (Wallach, *loc. cit.*), and limonene perbromide by stepwise reduction (Baeyer and Villiger, *loc. cit.*). Of these, the most important but little investigated are the thermal and alkali decomposition techniques. Known long ago, these techniques rest on the fact that under certain conditions bromine affords with terpenoids, at relatively low temperatures, high boiling products, which being heat and alkali labile, can be broken down to benzenoid counterparts without reduction (cf. Olsen, *Ber.*, 1948, 81, 131). Thus, the transformation of limonene to *p*-cymene effected *via* the perbromide, $C_{10}H_{13}Br_7$ (Baeyer and Villiger, *loc. cit.*), can be better accomplished by heating the tetrabromide, $C_{10}H_{16}Br_4$ (Olsen, *loc. cit.*); spontaneous cleavage of three moles of hydrogen bromide from the perbromide still leaves four atoms of bromine, which can only be expelled by reduction (Olsen, *loc. cit.*). From this and other conversions it is concluded that (i) the Baeyer-Villiger dehydrogenation method is based on false premises, (ii) there is no need to prepare 'fully' brominated derivatives, and (iii) it is incomplete bromination which offers a guarantee to successful aromatisation by heat and alkali (cf. Olsen, *loc. cit.*). A study was therefore undertaken on the bromine dehydrogenation of 3-carene, α -pinene, terpinolene, and terpineol to gain further confirmation of this conclusion, and also to demonstrate the two-way opening of the bicyclic terpenes leading to a mixture of cymenes.

EXPERIMENTAL

3-Carene, isolated by a two-fold fractionation of Indian turpentine oil of *Pinus longifolia* (Roxb) (Bareilly First Quality), has the following properties: b.p. 170-71°/760mm, n_D^{20} 1.4728, d_4^{20} 0.8614. Nitrosate, prepared from this oil, after recrystallisation from chloroform by addition of cold methanol melted at 147° (decomp.) (lit. 147.5°; Simonsen, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 117, 574).

α -Pinene was obtained by fractionation of a sample, kindly supplied by Hercules Powder Company, Wilmington, U.S.A., and has b.p. 156°/760mm, n_D^{20} 1.4657 and d_4^{20} 0.8592.

Terpinolene tetrabromide was prepared as follows. Cold bromine was added dropwise to terpinolene (b.p. 184-86°/760mm, n_D^{20} 1.4865) which had been dissolved in a mixture of amyl alcohol and diethyl ether (1:2) and cooled in a freezing mixture until coloured. The tetrabromide was precipitated with cold methanol. Solids separated were thrice precipitated from

chloroform with methanol. Crystals thus obtained melted at 116°; m.p. remained undepressed by an admixture with an authentic sample of terpinolene tetrabromide. Terpeneol has b.p. 218-19°/760mm, n_D^{20} 1.4829 and d_4^{20} 0.9332.

Dehydrogenations

3-Carene.—To cooled 3-carene (21.25g., 0.1562M) in a freezing mixture cold bromine (24.96g., 0.1562M) was added dropwise with occasional shaking. Addition of bromine was attended with very slight formation of hydrogen bromide. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 24 hours with copious evolution of HBr. The reaction mixture was then washed with 10% NaOH solution and steam-distilled (yield 15.2g.). The volatile portion was shaken with twice its volume of cold 80% H₂SO₄. Saturates thus obtained were separated in the usual manner and carefully fractionated to yield a cut (5.6g.), b.p. 170-80°/760mm, n_D^{20} 1.4886 and d_{30}^{30} 0.8592.

This oil (480mg.) was oxidised with potassium dichromate-sulphuric acid mixture (Leo *et al.*, *Curr. Sci.*, 1953, **22**, 112; *Bull. Nat. Inst. Sci., India*, 1959, No.12, 179). Total terephthalic and isophthalic acids amounted to 380mg. These were separated from each other as barium salts (Smith, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, **43**, 1921) (terephthalic acid: yield 270mg., dimethyl ester, m.p. 141°; isophthalic acid: yield 80mg., dimethyl ester, m.p. 65°).

α -Pinene.—On treatment with bromine (24.96g., 0.1562M) in a manner analogous to that of 3-carene, α -pinene (21.25g., 0.1562M) afforded saturates (ca. 3.5g., with b.p. 168-76°/760mm, n_D^{30} 1.4889). Oxidation of 500mg. of this oil with potassium dichromate-sulphuric acid mixture (Leo *et al.*, *loc. cit.*) and alkaline potassium permanganate gave respectively ca. 250mg. of terephthalic acid (nitro derivative, m. p. 269°; Lange *et al.*, *J. Chem. Ed.*, 1955, **32**, 40) and ca. 80mg. of *o*-phthalic acid (phthalanil, m.p. 270°).

Terpinolene.—Terpinolene tetrabromide (12g.) was heated under reflux for 1 hour, and then distilled (yield ca. 2g.). The distillate was treated with cold 80% H₂SO₄, and the saturates thus obtained were oxidised with potassium permanganate (Wallach, *Annalen*, 1891, **264**, 10; Solodskii, *Lesokhim Prom.*, 1940, **3**, *iv*, 8) to furnish *p*-(α -hydroxypropyl)-benzoic acid, m.p. 156°; mixed with an authentic sample of the acid, there was no depression in m.p.

Terpeneol.—To terpeneol (20g., 0.1297M), cooled in a freezing mixture, was added dropwise with occasional shaking cold bromine (20.69g., 0.1297M). The brominated mixture was refluxed with a solution of NaOH (20g.) in ethanol for 15 hours. The oily portion was separated in the usual manner and agitated with cold 80% H₂SO₄. Saturates obtained amounted to ca. 2.2g. and this, when oxidised with potassium permanganate (Wallach, *loc. cit.*), afforded *p*-(α -hydroxypropyl)-benzoic acid, m.p. 156°, undepressed when admixed with an authentic sample of the acid. Further, potassium dichromate-sulphuric acid oxidation of 400mg. of the saturates furnished ca. 200mg. of terephthalic acid (dimethyl ester, m.p. 141°).

DISCUSSION

Aromatisation of 3-carene (I) with bromine gave rise to *p*- and *m*-cymenes (VI & VII). Presence of these benzenoids was proved by their oxidation to terephthalic and isophthalic acids in amounts theoretically equivalent to 44.41% *p*-cymene and 13.47% *m*-cymene respectively. Thus it is evident that the terpene decyclises by fission of C₁-C₇ and C₆-C₇ linkages, and preferentially the former. The transformation clearly reveals the carbon framework in 3-carene, hitherto adduced from the results of its oxidative degradation (Simonsen, *loc. cit.*; Semmler and Schiller, *Ber.*, 1927, **60**, 1591) and hydrochlorination (Robinson, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, **27**, 247). Up to the present, no terpenoid has simultaneously furnished these cymenes with bromine; the

only terpenoid that afforded *m*-cymene, and that by the Baeyer-Villiger method (*Ber.*, 1898, **31**, 2067) is sylvestrene. Hence, the two-way aromatisation described herein constitutes a new reaction in terpene chemistry.

It has been reported earlier (Simonsen, *loc. cit.*) that with bromine in chloroform, 3-carene reacts readily, one mole of bromine being absorbed, but the dibromide is unstable and evolves hydrogen bromide. Now the addition of bromine to 3-carene, as described in the Experimental part, is also a smooth process, with very little evolution of hydrogen bromide. Fixation of bromine to the terpene can take place in two ways: (1) bromine saturates the double bond to yield the dibromide (II), assuming that the *cyclopropane* ring remains intact, and (2) bromine causes the cleavage of the *cyclopropane* ring two directionally at the C₁-C₇ and C₆-C₇ linkages to yield respectively the dibromides (III) and (IV). While the first possibility is in conformity with the normal addition of bromine to ethenoid linkage, the second possibility is justified because it is known that bromine can rupture *cyclopropanes*, as for instance in the conversion of *cyclopropane* into 1:3-dibromopropane (Gustavson, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1900, *ii*, **62**, 290). On refluxing, the dibromide (II) gives off hydrogen bromide, as has been indicated in the experimental section, and is known from the observation made by Simonsen (*loc. cit.*) to afford, probably, 3:7:7-trimethyl-2:4-*nor*caradiene (V), which suffers two-directional cleavage of the *cyclopropane* ring to provide *p*- and *m*-cymenes. The dibromides (III) and (IV) can yield *p*- and *m*-cymene respectively by expelling two moles of hydrogen bromide and subsequent rearrangement.

Coming to α -pinene (VIII), bromine is known to yield only *p*-cymene. This necessitates the unilateral fission of the C₁-C₆ bond of the terpene. Evidence is now presented to show that the C₅-C₆ bond can also break, leading to *o*-cymene (XI). Comparison of the yields of *tere*- and *ortho*-phthalic acids suggests that the favoured path of ring scission is at the C₁-C₆ bond. In the pinene series, reactions involving the formation of *o*-menthane derivatives are very rare (Perkin and Kay, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, **87**, 1066; Simonsen, "The Terpenes", Vol. II, Cambridge University Press, 2nd ed., 1949, pp. 168, 170; cf. Verghese and Yeddanapalli, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1957, **16B**, 224; Verghese, *ibid.*, 1959, **18B**, 270; this *Journal*, 1959, **36**, 155; cf. Klein, Hunt and Booth, U.S.P., 2,818,435/1957), and so the two-way aromatisation is of considerable theoretical importance.

Moreover, this conversion reveals the mode of incorporation of the *cyclobutane* ring system in the methylcyclohexane nucleus in α -pinene.

The mechanism to account for this transformation of α -pinene can be formulated in a manner similar to that of 3-carene, and involves the addition of bromine across the double bond to yield the dibromide (IX), which then loses two moles of hydrogen bromide to furnish the transient compound (X). Formation of the multiple linkage at the bridgehead position is contrary to the Bredt rule (*Ber.*, 1902, 35, 1286; *Annalen*, 1924, 437, 1). Of the two modes of stabilisation of (X) by decyclisation, theoretically the fission of the linkage $\text{C}_1\text{-C}_6$ should take precedence over that of $\text{C}_5\text{-C}_6$. Actually this is the case. More *p*- than *o*-cymene is obtained in the reaction.

Attention may now be directed to the aromatisation of terpinolene (XII). Already Wallach (*Annalen*, 1893, 275, 103) has indicated that the bromine atoms of terpinolene tetrabromide (XIII)

can be more easily cleaved than those of dipentene tetrabromide; the hydrocarbon from terpinolene tetrabromide has not been studied though it seems to be *p*-cymene. Conclusive evidence is now presented to confirm this by preparation of the derivative, *p*-(α -hydroxypropyl)-benzoic

acid. Steps leading to *p*-cymene are shown in the above scheme. The decomposition consists of the expulsion of three moles of hydrogen bromide, and in the reductive elimination of the remaining bromine atom with the liberated hydrogen bromide; the 8-bromo-*p*-cymene is only a hypothetical reaction intermediate.

Lastly, the aromatisation of terpineol (XV) may be considered. Saturation of the double bond in terpineol gives the dibromide (XVI), and this with alkali suffers dehydrobromination, dehydration, and then rearrangement to furnish *p*-cymene:

It may not be out of place to point out that Simonsen ("The Terpenes", Vol. I, Cambridge University Press, 2nd. ed., 1947, p. 262) has wrongly included this conversion among the examples of the Baeyer-Villiger method for dehydrogenation of cyclic bodies.

A common feature of these dehydrogenations is that excess of bromine has been strictly avoided. Thus, for 3-carene, α -pinene and terpineol, only molar proportion of bromine, which is half the quantity required for terpinolene, was used. Thus in agreement with Olsen (*loc. cit.*), the results of this investigation support the conclusion that the Baeyer-Villiger method is based on false premises and that there is no need to subject terpenoids to exhaustive bromination and later reduction for obtaining benzenoid counterparts.

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